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Thin silicon sensors for extreme fluences: A doping compensation strategy

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ABSTRACT

The Complex project aims at extending the operation range of silicon detectors as 4D trackers up to $5 \times 10^{17} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The project envisions achieving this unprecedented radiation tolerance through a novel comprehension of radiation damage saturation, and an innovative design for the Low-Gain Avalanche Diodes (LGADs) gain layer with compensated implants. This innovative LGAD design, featuring a co-implantation of acceptor and donor dopants, represents a paradigm shift in radiation-resistant sensor technology. It potentially enables compensated LGADs to maintain functionality at fluences exceeding $10^{17} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, significantly extending the operational lifetime of conventional LGAD sensors under extreme fluence conditions. This advantage is further enhanced by the inherent radiation tolerance of thin substrates. This work presents simulations and measurements from the first compensated LGAD production (late 2022, FBK foundry) before and after neutrons irradiation. Numerical modeling strategies using state-of-the-art Technology-CAD tools quantify the reduction in acceptor removal rate due to carbon co-implantation and investigate the behavior of donor removal under irradiation. This comprehensive approach paves the way for the development of highly efficient tracking detectors for future collider experiments.

1. Introduction

In the last decades, silicon detectors have been the workhorses of particle physics discoveries at colliders. Their exceptional tracking capabilities have revolutionized our understanding of the fundamental nature of matter. However, the ever-increasing instantaneous luminosity of collider experiments presents a formidable challenge in terms of radiation hardness. Conventional planar silicon detectors exhibit a significant performance degradation under extreme radiation environments. This limits their operational lifetime in future hadron colliders experiments, which demand efficient tracking detectors able to operate at expected fluences exceeding $10^{17} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Thin Low-Gain Avalanche Diodes (LGADs) emerge as promising candidates for 4D tracking in upcoming experiments, exhibiting excellent timing and tracking capabilities. Their internal signal amplification proves effective in mitigating radiation damage effects (e.g., charge collection efficiency loss) up to approximately $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Indeed,

a significant performance deterioration has been observed in standard LGADs above $5 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, when the acceptor removal effect almost completely neutralizes the charge multiplication mechanism [1].

Within this framework, the Complex project aims at extending the operational range of silicon detectors as 4D trackers up to $5 \times 10^{17} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The project envisions achieving this unprecedented radiation tolerance through a novel comprehension of radiation damage saturation and an innovative design for the gain layer of LGAD devices with compensated implants. Applying these breakthroughs to thin LGAD sensors (20–40 μm) with an internal gain of 10–20, enables the design of innovative silicon sensors operating efficiently up to the target fluence. Understanding and modeling the radiation damage effects up to $5 \times 10^{17} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ has the utmost importance, and state-of-the-art Technology CAD tools will be used for the purpose at hand. Additionally, the project will utilize measurements from the first batch

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Fig. 1. Gain as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGADs illuminated with an infrared laser after irradiation up to the fluence of $5 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Measurements were performed at $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a laser intensity equivalent to 4 MIPs. Dashed lines represent W12 (3–2), solid lines W13 (3–2+C).

of compensated LGADs, produced by FBK foundry in late 2022. Analyzing and comparing pre- and post-neutron irradiation measurements and simulations will provide crucial experimental data to validate the modeling strategies.

2. Compensated LGAD sensors

In compensated LGAD design, the gain layer results from the co-implantation of boron and phosphorus atoms in the same volume, underneath the readout electrode. The effective doping is given by the difference of the two implants, achieving a resulting doping profile similar to that of standard LGADs [2]. Both acceptor and donor atoms will undergo removal with irradiation, but strategical engineering of their implantation profiles can ensure their difference remains constant even with irradiation, preserving the multiplication power of the LGAD sensor and thus ensuring enhanced radiation resilience.

2.1. Test structures

The EXFLU1 batch, fabricated on 6-inch epitaxial wafers with a $30 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ active thickness, marked the first production run of compensated LGAD sensors by Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) at the end of 2022 [3]. Different combinations of acceptor (Boron) and donor (Phosphorus) doses with a constant doping difference of one (*i.e.* the standard LGAD gain layer), represented as 2–1, 3–2, and 5–4, have been explored to assess their impact on compensation effects. Within the 3–2 combination, one wafer (W13) received co-implantation of carbon alongside boron and phosphorus. Prior studies on standard LGADs have demonstrated the general benefits of carbon co-implantation in mitigating acceptor removal [1]. However, the presence of phosphorus introduces a new dynamic, and it is of utmost importance to understand how carbon co-implantation interacts with phosphorus in sensors' operation.

The next sections present a comparative analysis of test structure results from wafers W12 (without carbon co-implantation) and W13 (with carbon co-implantation) using the 3–2 dose combination. This comparison aims to assess the influence of carbon co-implantation on the sensor's performance under irradiation.

2.2. Gain characteristics in compensated LGAD sensors

The specific Transient Current Technique (TCT) setup employed for the characterization of the test structures is located at the Physics Department of Torino University. This setup utilizes an infrared picosecond laser with a 1060 nm wavelength to induce a signal within the sensors. The laser beam is focused with a lens, achieving a minimum spot size of $10 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$. The sensor output signal is amplified by a 40 dB

Cividec Broadband Amplifier, a low-noise current amplifier with an analog bandwidth of 2 GHz, and readout by a Teledyne Lecroy Oscilloscope (740Zi) with a sampling of 40 GSamples/s and a bandwidth of 4 GHz.

The gain of compensated LGAD sensors is measured as a function of the applied reverse bias, from test structures with an LGAD and a PIN sensor in the same die. The PIN diode serves as a calibration reference, correlating the measured signal to the expected response from a minimum ionizing particle (MIP) impinging the sensors. For a $30 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ active thickness, a MIP is estimated to generate a signal of approximately 0.3 fC.

Both the PIN and LGAD detectors are illuminated with identical infrared laser intensity. At the different bias voltages, the gain is then calculated by dividing the LGAD signal area by the average area of the PIN signals. For irradiated test structures, the PIN signal areas used for averaging are obtained at bias voltages below 400 V. This is because signal multiplication within the bulk region of the PIN diode occurs at higher bias voltages, which would skew the average and lead to inaccurate gain calculations for the LGAD.

The gain performances of compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation as a function of the reverse bias are shown in Fig. 1. Test structures of W12 (3–2) and W13 (3–2+C) have been irradiated at different fluences up to $5 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The tests were performed at a temperature of about $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and with an infrared laser intensity equivalent to ~ 4 MIPs. While not irradiated W12 and W13 exhibited similar behavior [3], W13 sensors demonstrated an improved radiation hardness compared to W12. Notably, at identical bias voltages, sensors from W13 displayed a three-fold gain increase over W12 when irradiated at the same fluence.

This observation suggests that co-implanting carbon alongside boron and phosphorus in the gain layer region effectively mitigates boron deactivation even in compensated LGAD sensors. This finding implies that the presence of phosphorus does not hinder the beneficial effect of carbon co-implantation, which appears to be consistent with its role in standard LGADs [4].

3. Donor removal

Understanding the interplay between acceptor and donor removal under irradiation is critical for the success of the compensated LGAD design. This necessitates a thorough investigation of both removal processes, their relative rates, and potential interdependence. Maintaining a constant difference between acceptor and donor concentration (p^+ and n^+ dopants) with irradiation, is the key aspect of a stable gain layer multiplication mechanism.

Acceptor removal in p-type silicon sensors is a well-documented phenomenon, and its impact on performance degradation is extensively studied [5,6]. However, the understanding of donor removal is less complete. While some research has been conducted, knowledge of its mechanisms and rates is limited to a specific range of fluences and dopant concentrations [7,8]. A deeper understanding of the underlying physics governing dopant removal under irradiation can guide further optimization in terms of co-implantation strategies and defects engineering, avoiding premature performance degradation.

3.1. TCAD approach to the study of donor removal

State-of-the-art Synopsys[®] Sentaurus Technology CAD (TCAD) suite of software offers advanced simulation tools for designing and analyzing semiconductor detectors, enabling performance optimization [9]. The pursued approach to study how quickly donor doping is deactivated is to compare TCAD simulations with experimental measurements at the different fluences, mainly focusing on C-V characteristics. This analysis aims to assess the donor removal coefficient. The experimental data comes from the first batch of compensated LGADs [3].

Fig. 2. TCAD simulations and experimental measurements of not-irradiated Compensated LGADs belonging to the 3–2 acceptor-donor doses combination. Carbon is also co-implanted in the gain layer region of W13.

Fig. 3. TCAD simulations and experimental measurements of Compensated LGADs belonging to the 3–2 acceptor-donor doses combination and irradiated at a fluence of $1.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{eq}/cm^2$. Carbon is also co-implanted in the gain layer region of W13. The bands represent the variability of the measurements.

C-V measurements were performed at a temperature of $+20$ °C and a frequency of 1–2 kHz.

To ensure consistency and minimize geometric discrepancies, the TCAD model was initially calibrated by achieving good agreement between simulated and measured C-V characteristics of non-irradiated PIN diodes. PIN diodes offer a simpler structure compared to LGADs due to the absence of a gain layer, facilitating the calibration process. The substrate thickness and the bulk doping concentration were tuned until an agreement was reached with C-V measurements.

Thereafter, the n^+ and p^+ profiles of the compensated gain layer were added to the test structure layout within the TCAD environment. These implant profiles were derived by fitting Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) [10] measurement data and fine-tuned to agree with the experimental C-Vs of not irradiated compensated LGADs. Fig. 2 shows such agreement for W12(3–2) and W13(3–2+C). The curves result superimposed, suggesting a minimal influence of carbon on the overall device behavior under these conditions.

The next step involved simulating the device's response under radiation exposure. The most recent release of the Perugia radiation damage model was used in the TCAD environment [11–13] to suitably account not only for the combined bulk and surface radiation damage effects but also for the acceptor creation of the bulk, and the acceptor removal mechanism of the gain layer, both described by the Torino

Fig. 4. TCAD simulations and experimental measurements of Compensated LGADs belonging to the 3–2 acceptor-donor doses combination and irradiated at a fluence of $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{eq}/cm^2$. Carbon is also co-implanted in the gain layer region of W13. The bands represent the variability of the measurements.

parameterizations [1]. The acceptor removal effect in LGAD sensors is described by an exponential function with an acceptor removal coefficient (c_A) and dependence on the initial acceptor concentration. This approach can likely be extended to describe donor removal by incorporating a donor removal coefficient (c_D) and assuming similar dependencies on the initial donor concentration and removal rate.

More in general, the removal of acceptor and donor atoms in the gain layer region is modeled with the following law:

$$N_{A,D}(\phi) = N_{A,D}(0) \cdot e^{-c_{A,D} \cdot \phi}$$

where $c_{A,D}$ is the acceptor (donor) removal coefficient, $N_{A,D}(0)$ is the initial acceptor (donor) concentration, and ϕ is the fluence in n_{eq}/cm^2 .

We compared simulated and measured C-V curves at $1.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{eq}/cm^2$ (Fig. 3) and $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{eq}/cm^2$ (Fig. 4). While c_A is known from investigations on standard LGADs [1], c_D was assessed by fitting simulated C-V curves to experimental data. By analyzing the region of the C-Vs before the knee that describes the depletion of the gain layer, we determined that the donor removal rate exceeds the acceptor removal rate. Indeed, in this region simulations fall well in the middle of the different bands at the different fluences using values of $c_D > c_A$. Shaded bands represents the variability among multiple measurements from the same wafer under identical conditions.

The simulated curves of W12 have been obtained considering $c_A = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-16} cm^2$ and $c_D = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-16} cm^2$. The curves of W13 were modeled with a lower $c_A = 8.26 \cdot 10^{-17} cm^2$, thus considering a slowing down in acceptor removal due to the carbon co-implantation in the gain layer region. The same value for c_D was applied to both W12 and W13.

The achieved agreement between simulations and experimental data suggests a potentially faster removal rate for donors compared to acceptors ($c_D > c_A$). This observation provides the first indication of a difference in removal kinetics between the two dopant species in the gain layer. Notably, the consistency of this agreement across both wafers, suggests that the presence of donor doping might not alter the established acceptor removal mechanism and carbon effect observed in standard LGADs.

Conclusion

The Complex project explores a novel approach to extend the operational range of silicon detectors as 4D trackers, targeting unprecedented fluences of up to $5 \cdot 10^{17} n_{eq}/cm^2$. This is achieved through a combination of a deeper understanding of radiation damage saturation and the development of compensated LGAD sensors with co-implanted boron and phosphorus atoms in the gain layer region.

Initial measurements on the first batch of compensated LGADs (produced by FBK in late 2022) demonstrate promising results. Notably, W13 sensors with co-implanted carbon exhibited a three-fold gain increase compared to W12 sensors (without carbon co-implantation) after irradiation at the same fluence ($5 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$). This suggests that carbon co-implantation effectively mitigates boron deactivation even in the presence of phosphorus.

TCAD simulations were employed to study donor removal under irradiation. By comparing simulations with C-V measurements at different fluences, a potentially faster removal rate for donors compared to acceptors was observed ($c_D > c_A$). This finding provides valuable insights into the different removal kinetics of dopant species within the gain layer.

Further investigations are planned to refine the understanding of donor removal mechanisms and their interplay with acceptor removal. This knowledge will guide further optimization of co-implantation strategies and defect engineering for achieving highly efficient and radiation-tolerant tracking detectors for future collider experiments.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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